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LINGUISTIC INDEPENDENCE: THE VIEWS AND CONCEPTS OF GREAT STEPPE THINKERS ON LEXICAL BORROWING

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Introduction. The Kazakh people have long expressed the importance of interpersonal and intersocietal communication through sociolinguistic wisdom reflected in sayings such as: “*Horses neigh to one another, people communicate through language*” and “*Human beings depend on one another.*” Indeed, relationships and interactions among peoples and states across cultural, historical, political, economic, and other spheres cannot be realized without language. Communication inevitably occurs through the involvement of two or more languages. This is because neither the life of an entire nation nor that of an individual can be fully sustained by a single language. There is no language in the world that possesses such a broad (maximal) functional capacity as to satisfy all human communicative needs. Likewise, there is no language serving only a narrow (minimal) function limited to the daily interactions of two individuals. All languages in the world exist and function within the continuum between these broad and narrow communicative domains [1, p. 24].

Consequently, individuals in society are often required to acquire and use another language in addition to their native language, and sometimes even several languages. Such circumstances inevitably lead to language contact and interaction. Linguistic interaction primarily results in lexical borrowing from one language into another. The process of lexical borrowing is a universal phenomenon that occurs both among culturally advanced societies and among societies with relatively slower cultural development; therefore, it is an unavoidable linguistic process inherent in all languages.

In the era of globalization, one of the principal conditions for preserving national identity is the strengthening of linguistic immunity. Today, the rapid flow of information and increasing cultural integration exert significant pressure on the natural structure of language, particularly on its lexical system. In this regard, the concept of *linguistic independence* is no longer merely a philological term but has evolved into an important factor of state security and national integrity.

Language contamination, the uncontrolled influx of loanwords, and the gradual displacement of native lexical units represent potentially harmful phenomena capable of altering a nation’s cognitive framework and worldview. However, this issue is not a recent development. Thinkers and scholars originating from the Great Steppe have consistently emphasized the importance of linguistic purity and the principles governing lexical bor-

rowing throughout different historical periods. From the logical reflections of Al-Farabi to the ideas of linguistic equality proposed by Mahmud al-Kashgari, and from the scientific concepts of the Alash intellectuals – Akhmet Baitursynuly, Nazyr Torequlov, and Qudaybergen Zhubanov – a shared concern and intellectual continuity regarding language preservation can be observed.

Examining the perspectives of these scholars concerning lexical borrowing constitutes an essential key to addressing contemporary terminological challenges in Kazakh linguistics and strengthening linguistic independence. This article analyzes the views of prominent scholars of the Great Steppe regarding the balance between enriching linguistic resources and protecting them from excessive external influences, while also evaluating the contemporary relevance of their ideas within current language policy.

Materials and Methods. The source base of this study consists of fundamental works produced by prominent thinkers and linguists of the Great Steppe from both the medieval and modern periods. In particular, the research draws upon Al-Farabi’s reflections on the relationship between logic and language, Mahmud al-Kashgari’s works demonstrating the lexical richness of Turkic languages, as well as the scholarly works of A.Baitursynuly, N.Torequlov, and Q.Zhubanov, who established the theoretical foundations of Kazakh linguistics. Contemporary studies addressing issues of lexicology and terminology in Kazakh linguistics were also utilized as supporting sources.

To accomplish the objectives of the study, a set of interconnected scientific methods was employed. The descriptive method was used to systematize and present the views of historical scholars regarding linguistic independence and lexical borrowing. The comparative-historical method enabled an examination of the continuity and evolution of linguistic norms and principles of lexical borrowing from the medieval period to the present day. Component analysis was applied to determine the semantic structure of concepts such as *linguistic independence*, *lexical transfer*, *loanword*, and *barbarism*. Furthermore, methods of logical synthesis and generalization were employed to consolidate the theoretical perspectives of scholars from different historical periods and to formulate a scientifically grounded framework aimed at strengthening the linguistic immunity of the contemporary Kazakh language.

Literature Review / State of the Problem. Unlike other forms of language contact, such as

code-switching and code-mixing, the process of lexical borrowing does not require language users to possess profound knowledge of another language. Nor does it necessarily involve direct interaction between representatives of two cultures. In this process, only lexical material directly comes into contact and functions within another linguistic system.

The study of language contact and related phenomena, particularly the process of lexical borrowing, represents a complex issue with a well-established research tradition in both domestic and international linguistics. Currently, this problem has become increasingly relevant and continues to attract the attention of numerous scholars. This is primarily due to the significant expansion of international relations during the late twentieth and early twenty-first centuries. Today, such interactions occur at unprecedented speed through internet technologies that have become accessible at all levels of society. Moreover, linguistic contact has intensified both among speakers of different languages and through political discourse, scientific publications, and mass media.

The concept of *lexical borrowing* in linguistics is characterized by semantic ambiguity. In general linguistics, many scholars distinguish between the concepts of *borrowing* and *loanword*, proposing that the term *borrowing* should be used to denote *language interaction or mutual linguistic influence*. Other researchers, however, do not differentiate between these concepts and primarily associate borrowing with loanwords. For example, in Kazakh linguistics, the term *loanword* is commonly used to denote all linguistic units originating from other languages, including words, phrases, morphemes, syntactic constructions, and others. This situation resembles the parallel use of the terms *speech culture* and *language culture* in Kazakh, which are often employed interchangeably. In Russian linguistics, the general term *zaimstvovanie* (“borrowing”) refers to all linguistic units adopted from another language, whereas *zaimstvovannoe slovo* (“borrowed word”) specifically denotes a lexical unit borrowed from another language.

Considering lexical borrowing as a form of language contact, S.V. Kudryashova, while analyzing its terminological meaning, states: “Some linguists regard borrowing as a process, whereas others understand it as the result of that process. Many foreign linguists characterize borrowing as a process that results in the transfer of linguistic units from one language to another. Other scholars view borrowing as elements transferred from another language that continue to exist within a language after interaction has ended, that is, as a consequence of language contact” [2, p. 68].

The definition most closely aligned with the objectives of our research is proposed by Profes-

sor Sabira Isakova, Doctor of Philological Sciences: “*Loanwords are foreign linguistic elements (words, phrases, suffixes, etc.) transferred from one language into another as a result of interlingual interaction (contact)*” [3].

Thus, in this study, the term *lexical borrowing* refers to all borrowed elements originating from foreign languages (words, morphemes, syntactic structures, and others), as well as the transfer of lexical units adapted into the lexical system of another language. The process of lexical borrowing is considerably broader and more frequent than the transfer of grammatical, derivational, or phonetic elements.

The process of lexical borrowing can be understood in two senses. In the broad sense, lexical borrowing refers to the transfer of various linguistic elements from one language to another and their subsequent adaptation within the recipient language. In the narrow sense, it denotes linguistic elements transferred from one language into another and functioning within that linguistic system. Based on this understanding, the following types of borrowing may be distinguished:

1. **Loanwords** (the most common type of lexical borrowing);
2. **Phonetic borrowing** (a relatively rare type, depending on the degree of contact between languages);
3. **Morphemic borrowing** (typically occurring within word structures);
4. **Syntactic borrowing** (resulting from the influence of foreign syntactic constructions);
5. **Semantic borrowing** (the emergence of a new meaning in a word under the influence of a foreign language model, i.e., semantic calquing) [3, p. 29].

As a result of long-term historical interaction and contact among languages, lexical borrowing occupies a significant place within the vocabularies of many languages. The channels of borrowing may be oral, literary, or written. During oral transmission, borrowed words tend to undergo greater external modification than through written transmission. If a word enters a language simultaneously with the introduction of a new object or concept from another culture, its meaning generally remains unchanged. However, when a new lexical unit enters a language as a synonym of an already existing word, semantic distinctions emerge, often resulting in modifications to the original meaning.

In linguistics, borrowing from other languages is considered an objective historical phenomenon. However, the qualitative characteristics of this process and its impact on a language’s internal system vary significantly. It is important not to confuse *loanwords* with *barbarisms* within scholarly discourse. A *loanword* is a linguistic unit that has become fully adapted to the phonetic, grammatical, and morphological norms of the recipient

language and is perceived similarly to native lexical items. For example, according to A. Baitursynuly, words that enter the Kazakh language and conform to its phonetic rules gradually become part of the language's native lexical stock [4, p. 89]. A *barbarism*, on the other hand, refers to a foreign element that remains incompatible with the structural norms of a language and creates stylistic inconsistency or linguistic contamination. In this regard, the prominent linguist L.P. Krysin, in his work *Foreign Words in the Context of Contemporary Social Life*, notes that barbarisms may pose a threat to the aesthetic and structural integrity of a language [5]. Therefore, while loanwords may serve as indicators of linguistic development, barbarisms may be regarded as manifestations of linguistic expansion.

The land of Kazakhstan, stretching across the vast territory between Altai and Atyrau, the Irtysh and Volga rivers, and the Saryarka steppe and Alatau mountains, shares borders with five countries: Russia in the northwest, China in the east, and the culturally related nations of Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, and Kyrgyzstan in the south. Throughout various historical periods, this immense steppe region, together with its language, customs, daily life, and socio-economic structure, experienced the influence of Chinese, Mongolian, Arabic-Persian, Russian, and European cultures transmitted through Russian mediation. As a result, the contemporary Kazakh lexical system contains borrowed words derived primarily from four languages: Arabic, Persian, Mongolian, and Russian [6, p. 136].

How did lexical borrowing from these languages into Kazakh occur, and how might such processes continue in the future? Why does one language borrow words from another, and what are the underlying reasons and conditions for this phenomenon? What principles and regularities govern lexical borrowing? What are the general and language-specific approaches to this issue? How has this matter been addressed within the traditional linguistic practices of the Kazakh people? Naturally, answering all of these questions exceeds the scope of a single study. Nevertheless, this article seeks to contribute to the understanding of one aspect of this complex issue. Therefore, the present study provides an overview of the perspectives and reflections of prominent thinkers of the Great Steppe regarding these linguistic concerns.

Results and Discussion. The medieval thinker of the Great Steppe, Al-Farabi, explained why words from one language are transferred into another and how societies adopt such lexical elements:

"If a religion or a part of it is adopted from another people, the introducer of that religion may sometimes use names derived from the canons of that religion while preserving their mean-

ings, although the word itself may undergo modification. The sounds of the word and their structure are represented through the letters and structures of the receiving people. This is necessary in order to facilitate pronunciation" [7, p. 83].

If we examine the scholar's statement carefully, it becomes evident that although a borrowed word may enter another language while preserving its original meaning, changes may occur in its pronunciation and structural form. Thus, the pronunciation and orthographic representation of borrowed words become adapted to the linguistic nature of the recipient language. Examples of such adaptation in contemporary Kazakh usage include *samovar* → *samauryrn*, *Wikipedia* → *Uikipediya*, and *yarmarka* → *zhärmengke*.

The eminent thinker Al-Farabi also emphasized that when a recipient language possesses a sufficiently developed conceptual understanding of truth and falsehood, its own word-formation mechanisms can be employed to express new concepts. In this regard, he states: *"If dialectics and sophistry emerge within a people and their representatives perceive the necessity of designating ideas for which no terms previously existed because such concepts had been unknown to them, they create words accordingly. They construct these words from their own linguistic elements or assign existing names based on similarities with already known concepts"* [7, p. 83].

Examples of this phenomenon may be observed in the replacement or adaptation of foreign lexical items through native equivalents, such as *potential* → *äleuet* ("potential"), *status* → *märtebe* ("status"), *transport* → *kölik* ("transport"), and *traffic light* → *bağdarsham* ("traffic light").

One of the most renowned works of the eleventh century, the dictionary *Diwan Lughat al-Turk* (*Compendium of the Turkic Dialects*), authored by Mahmud al-Kashgari, demonstrates that although Arabic terms and titles were employed in the naming of books and sections for the sake of clarity and accessibility, a profound sense of devotion and respect toward the Turkic language can be felt throughout the work. For instance, the author's statement that he *"made the Turkic language run equally in competition with Arabic, like two horses racing side by side"*, and his remark that *"Since I kept in mind the need for people to find words clearly and use them with interest, I made the work concise, retained words in active use, and discarded those that had fallen out of use. This path I followed is the correct and proper one"*, indicate that loanwords entering from Arabic had already undergone adaptation according to the structural norms of Turkic languages [8, p. 37].

Furthermore, his statement that *"For learners and interested readers to find the necessary words quickly and easily, I labored for many years, arranging words in their proper places. I clarified*

obscurities, made them more comprehensible, softened errors, and corrected them" suggests that he personally introduced modifications to some lexical items [8, p. 36].

Therefore, this work, which serves as the first encyclopedic reference source of the Turkic world and Turkic languages, should continue to function as a model and guideline in contemporary scholarship for understanding the principles of lexical borrowing and establishing criteria for the acceptance of foreign lexical elements. In this regard, the observation made by A. Egeubai, who translated the work and authored its introduction, deserves special attention: *"The study and dissemination of this invaluable treasure enriches spiritual life with unique qualities that we had not previously fully recognized and reveals the deep-rooted characteristics of our linguistic culture that had nourished its foundations since ancient times"* [8, p. 26].

The issue of borrowing from other languages continued to be resolved through the natural principles of linguistic selection not only during the medieval period but also during the later stages of the consolidation of the Kazakh nation. The primary reason for this was the civic consciousness of the people, their close social relations, economic organization, and established cultural traditions, which unified the Kazakh people, consolidated their settlements, brought them together under a common identity, and enabled them to communicate through a shared language and cultural framework.

In this regard, the prominent Alash intellectual A. Baitursynuly states: *"The Kazakh people should possess a noble language and a proper orthography. Why? Because the Kazakhs have preserved their ancestral occupations. The Kazakhs lived separately and independently without excessive interaction with others. The Kazakhs, among Turkic peoples, did not distort their language under the influence of foreign writing systems. If a few foreign words entered from outside, the Kazakhs would assimilate and reshape them according to the patterns of their own language. Unless affected by foreign influence, foreign writing systems, or changes in occupation and traditions, there is absolutely no reason to claim that the Kazakh language itself has changed. Therefore, there are no grounds to consider Kazakh a transformed language..."* [4, pp. 395–396].

However, according to Baitursynuly and subsequent scholars, this linguistic purity and originality of the Kazakh language began to deteriorate after Kazakhstan became part of the Russian Empire.

Professor Q. Zhubanov writes: *"...After becoming part of Russia, communication weakened, the unity of the Kazakh people disintegrated, social structures fragmented, and consequently the*

formerly unified cultural fabric of the Kazakhs began to unravel, fragment, and disperse" [9, p. 440].

He further notes: *"Kazakh lands were divided, migration routes were interrupted, and each clan, village, and household became territorially confined. Communication diminished. Kazakhs in different regions were forced to sustain themselves under varying circumstances, gradually moving toward separation and the disintegration of cultural unity. Some of what are now referred to as Kazakh dialects emerged during this period as a consequence of such fragmentation. Consequently, the Kazakh language itself entered a process of disintegration. Had this process continued uninterrupted, the complete disappearance of the Kazakh language would have been possible. Furthermore, the Tsarist government disseminated religious influence as a means of controlling the Kazakh population"*.

Zhubanov further argues that discussions of Russian and broader imperial cultural influence on Kazakhstan often emphasized only its beneficial aspects while neglecting its potentially harmful consequences [9, p. 441].

Similarly, A. Baitursynuly observed: *"Borrowing may occur both during the subjugation of one nation by another and during peaceful interaction between nations. Similarities in religion, customs, morality, social organization, inclinations, instincts, psychology, and other forms facilitate the processes of borrowing and cultural interaction"*.

However, he continues: *"Such conditions did not exist for the cultural development of the Turkic peoples living within Russia. There were no similar forms of life between them and the only people from whom something could potentially be adopted. Furthermore, those who governed pursued policies of conquest, Russification, and Slavification toward non-native peoples"* [4, p. 420].

As if continuing the same policy of Russification as its inherited legacy, the Soviet government imposed the requirement that foreign words entering the Kazakh language either directly from Russian or through Russian mediation *"should not undergo any modifications and must be pronounced and written exactly as they are in Russian."* Concerning this issue, Sh. Qurmanbaiuly, a scholar specializing in Kazakh terminology studies, notes in the introduction to N. Torequlov's work *A Few Words on Foreign Terms*: *"It is well known that in the formation of our national terminological system, due to both linguistic and extralinguistic factors, we have extensively adopted ready-made terms from other languages. Particularly since the 1930s, when the objective was to establish a Soviet terminological system based on the Russian language, terms from European languages were accepted without modification in*

their Russian forms. Since this direction remained unchanged for approximately seventy years, the expansion of our lexical stock through externally borrowed terminology gradually became a tradition" [10, p. 3].

This observation accurately characterizes the current situation regarding lexical borrowing in the Kazakh language.

The views of Alash intellectuals who worked tirelessly alongside A. Baitursynuly in promoting the development of the Kazakh language – including E.Omaruly, N.Torequlov, H.Dosmukhameduly, T.Shonanuly, J.Aimauly, M.Zhumabayuly, Q.Kemenrepyly, and others – did not differ substantially with regard to the issue of borrowing foreign words. Although they maintained individual perspectives concerning the use of native linguistic resources and the adaptation of foreign lexical items to the phonetic and structural norms of Kazakh, they ultimately reached a common conclusion.

This collective decision was officially approved at the First Congress of Kazakh Scientific Workers held in Orenburg in June 1924. Since a detailed analysis of each scholar's views exceeds the scope of this article, their shared perspectives may be summarized through A.Baitursynuly's speech delivered at the First All-Union Turkological Congress held in Baku in 1926.

In his report, Baitursynuly noted: *"In connection with this, we were compelled to express concepts and ideas previously absent from the people's experience through Kazakh words and word combinations and were therefore obliged to represent them through our native language."* He subsequently proposed the following four principles:

The first principle concerns adopting Kazakh words that correspond semantically to foreign terms. According to Baitursynuly, this approach prevents linguistic stratification and avoids the emergence of separate linguistic forms for social groups – specifically, a distinction between the language of the educated and the uneducated, or between elites and ordinary people.

The second principle states that if equivalent lexical items do not exist in Kazakh, they should be borrowed from linguistically related languages. This principle is based on two considerations:

although many words in related languages may not possess identical forms, they often share common roots and are therefore easier to understand, hear, and pronounce than words originating from unrelated languages;

Turkic peoples have historically maintained and continue to maintain close interaction, making lexical items from one Turkic language potentially familiar to speakers of another, even where etymological roots do not entirely coincide.

The third principle involves accepting internationally recognized terms with modifications

corresponding to the linguistic nature of Kazakh. Baitursynuly further argued that if native Kazakh equivalents exist, both forms should be used simultaneously, allowing society itself to determine preference through usage.

In relation to this principle, he further stated:

"By internationally used terms we mean the widely distributed modern European terms, but not Arabic terms. We prioritize them because at present we are moving closer to European rather than Arabic culture. All achievements of European culture may be fully represented through European languages. However, terms adopted from these languages must conform to Kazakh speech; that is, the phonetic laws of our language arising from its habitual articulatory patterns must be applied to them. This is absolutely necessary if foreign words are to become our own words" (translation ours).

The fourth principle asserts that all non-Kazakh words incompatible with the linguistic nature of Kazakh should undergo transformation according to Kazakh pronunciation patterns. According to this principle:

first, all foreign sounds absent in Kazakh should be replaced with corresponding native sounds;

second, foreign affixes should be replaced with Kazakh affixes;

third, double sounds should be simplified into single sounds;

fourth, foreign endings should be modified according to the phonetic requirements of Kazakh pronunciation.

Examples include: *Orenburg* → *Orynbor*, *Samar* → *Samar*, *pukhovoi* → *bökebai*, *pokrov* → *bogyr*, *Adamovskii* → *Adamau*, and others [4, p. 423].

As a result, national principles governing lexical borrowing began to emerge and become institutionalized. Owing to the efforts of highly qualified Alash intellectuals of that period, this process developed dynamically in various directions, leading to the expansion of the word-formation and terminology-building capacities of the Kazakh language. Loanwords became adapted to the linguistic nature of the language, new terminological units were created on the basis of native linguistic resources, and it was convincingly demonstrated that scientific knowledge could be acquired and developed through the Kazakh language itself. Consequently, until the second half of the 1930s, the Kazakh language entered an unprecedented period of development.

However, beginning in the second half of the 1930s, national languages became subject to systematic restrictions and faced severe difficulties. As noted, *"The process of restriction began with the Resolution of the Council of People's Commissars of the USSR and the Central Committee of the*

Communist Party (March 13, 1938) regarding compulsory Russian language instruction in schools of national republics and regions, as well as the Resolution of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Kazakhstan and the Council of People's Commissars of Kazakhstan (April 5, 1938) concerning compulsory Russian language instruction in Kazakh schools" [11, p. 67].

From that point onward, the extensive efforts of Alash intellectuals led by A. Baitursynuly in developing the national language were rejected and characterized as *"the deviation of Alash activists"* and *"the spread of purism"*. It was argued that concepts could not be expressed without words borrowed from Russian, Latin, Greek, English, German, and other languages, and the Kazakh language was consequently regarded as incapable of generating scientific terminology.

Concerning this misguided policy, Sh. Qurmanbaiuly provides the following assessment: *"Today, while defending orthographic principles established during the Soviet period, we frequently regard attempts to adapt foreign words in the media to the characteristics of the national language as disorder or anarchy. In reality, however, the roots of the current inconsistency should be sought in the 1930s. The real linguistic anarchy and suppression of national language characteristics began precisely during that period. The foundations of some rigid principles that have now become fixed rules within our orthography were established then"* [12, p. 14].

Thus, the distorted policy that had served exclusively the interests and dominance of the Russian language during the Soviet era eventually came to an end, creating opportunities for the implementation of a national language policy conducive to the development of the Kazakh language. Beginning in the 1990s, the development of national principles for lexical borrowing and scientific terminology became a significant priority in Kazakhstan.

Nevertheless, numerous unresolved issues and challenges remain. Therefore, efforts in this sphere should continue to be guided by the intrinsic laws governing language, as understood and identified by the great thinkers of the Great Steppe who dedicated themselves to this cause. Their ideas, principles, and theoretical foundations should continue to guide future language development policies. This is because continuity between the linguistic heritage of historical figures and the perspectives of contemporary scholars constitutes the scientific basis for strengthening linguistic immunity and preserving linguistic independence in the era of globalization.

Conclusion. The study of the intellectual heritage of the thinkers of the Great Steppe and prominent figures of Kazakh linguistics demonstrates that the concept of *linguistic independence* forms

an inseparable component of national identity. Beginning with Al-Farabi and Mahmud al-Kashgari and subsequently systematized through the works of Alash intellectuals, the issue of linguistic purity has acquired renewed strategic significance within the context of globalization.

In summary, achieving linguistic independence requires adherence to the following principles:

1. Revitalizing the national phonological filter for borrowed words proposed by A. Baitursynuly;
2. Prioritizing internal linguistic resources over external sources in terminology formation;
3. Establishing a scientifically grounded system of linguistic immunity capable of protecting language norms from barbarisms and foreign elements.

The principles proposed by the thinkers of the Great Steppe concerning lexical borrowing should not be regarded merely as a historical legacy; rather, they serve as a guiding framework for strengthening the status of the Kazakh language as a state language and determining its future development.

Finally, the issue of lexical borrowing may be summarized through the words of the distinguished Alash intellectual Eldes Omaruly: *"If the laws of language change, if the language becomes distorted, and if the language of science becomes separated from the language of ordinary people, then science itself will become something inaccessible to the general public, like an object beyond a vast river. Therefore, the laws of language should not be violated. The language should be preserved in its purest possible form. Existing sounds of the language should not be lost, nor should the language be contaminated by foreign sounds absent from it. Scientific terminology may indeed be borrowed from developed nations; however, when such words are incorporated into Kazakh, they should be transformed into forms resembling native Kazakh words by replacing foreign sounds with Kazakh equivalents and adapting them according to the fundamental laws of the Kazakh language"* [13, p. 75].

These principles should serve as important guidelines in the development of the new Kazakh alphabet and its orthographic rules within the framework of contemporary spiritual modernization initiatives.

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Lingvistik mustaqillik: buyuk dasht mutafakirlarining chet tillardan so'z o'zlashtirish haqidagi qarashlari va konsepsiyalari

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Maqolada tillarning o'zaro aloqasi jarayonida so'z o'zlashishi, uning lingvistik va ekstralingvistik sabablari hamda omillari ko'rib chiqiladi. Tadqiqotning asosiy obyekti sifatida Buyuk Dasht mutafakirlarining chet tillardan so'z qabul qilish qonuniyatlari va milliy tamoyillariga oid qarashlari hamda konsepsiyalari tanlangan. Mualliflar o'rta asr olimlari Abu Nasr Forobiy va Mahmud Qoshg'ariyning asarlaridagi so'z o'zlashishi bilan bog'liq dastlabki lingvistik g'oyalarni tahlil qilib, qozoq tilining o'zlashgan so'zlarni o'z tabiatiga moslashtirish va og'zaki ravishda qabul qilish tajribasini tarixiy nuqtai nazardan aniqlaydilar. Maqolada podsho Ros-siyasi va sovet davridagi til siyosatining qozoq tilining tabiiy rivojlanish qonuniyatlariga ko'rsatgan ta'siri atroflicha tahlil qilinadi. XX asr boshlarida A. Baitursinuli boshchiligidagi Alash ziyolilarining qozoq tilini ilm-fan tili sifatida shakllantirishdagi faoliyati hamda ularning boshqa tillardan so'z qabul qilishning ilmiy-nazariy tamoyillarini ishlab chiqishdagi o'rni kompleks tarzda yoritiladi. Tadqiqot natijasida globallashtirish sharoitida qozoq tilining lingvistik mustaqilligini saqlash maqsadida tarixiy tamoyillarni zamonaviy til qurilishi jarayonida qo'llashning dolzarbligi asoslab beriladi.

Лингвистическая независимость: взгляды и концепции мыслителей великой степи о лексическом заимствовании

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В статье рассматриваются процесс заимствования слов в ходе взаимодействия языков, его лингвистические причины и экстралингвистические условия. Основной объект исследования – концептуальные идеи и выводы мыслителей Великой степи относительно закономерностей и национальных принципов принятия иноязычной лексики. Авторы анализируют первые лингвистические представления о заимствовании в трудах средневековых ученых аль-Фараби и М.Кашгари, выявляя исторический опыт казахского языка по устному освоению и адаптации заимствованной лексики к своей природе. В статье рассматривается процесс нарушения закономерностей естественного развития казахского языка вследствие языковой политики царской России и советской эпохи. Всесторонне изучается деятельность интеллектуалов «Алаш» во главе с А.Байтурсинулы по формированию казахского языка как языка науки в начале XX века, а также обоснованные ими научно-теоретические принципы принятия слов из других языков. В результате исследования обосновывается актуальность руководства данными историческими принципами в современном языковом строительстве для сохранения лингвистической независимости казахского языка в условиях глобализации.

Linguistic independence: the views and concepts of great steppe thinkers on lexical borrowing

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The article examines the process of lexical borrowing during language interaction, its linguistic causes, and extralinguistic conditions. The primary focus of the study is the conceptual ideas and conclusions of the Great Steppe thinkers regarding the patterns and national principles of adopting foreign vocabulary. The authors analyze early linguistic concepts of borrowing in the works of medieval scholars al-Farabi and M. Kashgari, identifying the historical experience of the Kazakh language in the oral assimilation and adaptation of loanwords to its inherent nature. The article analyzes the disruption of the natural development patterns of the Kazakh language resulting from the language policies of Tsarist Russia and the Soviet era. It provides a comprehensive study of the activities of the "Alash" intellectuals, led by A. Baitursynuly, in establishing Kazakh as a language of science in the early 20th century, as well as the scientific and theoretical principles they developed for adopting words from other languages. As a result of the study, the relevance of following these historical principles in modern linguistic construction is substantiated to preserve the linguistic independence of the Kazakh language in the context of globalization.